

INDUSTRIES AND SECTORS: ISSUES AND POLICIES

**INNOVATION IN THE CANADIAN
TEXTILE INDUSTRY**

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JEL Classifications: L67, O31

Keywords: Innovation, textile industry, manufacturing, innovation activities, business strategy

Abstract: This paper provides a descriptive analysis of the innovation and business strategies of Canadian textile firms. The results show that the textile industry is in a state of decline due mainly to competitive pressures resulting from economic and regulatory changes. The results also show that while the industry recognizes the need for innovation, the current strategies and practices do not seem to be aligned to their strategic goals of fostering innovation.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.15208/pieb.2013.09>

Vol.13 (2), PP.32-48

Source: Kollarova S., Persaud A., 2013. "Innovation in the Canadian textile industry", *Perspectives of Innovations, Economics & Business*, Vol.13(2), pp.32-48, <http://dx.doi.org/10.15208/pieb.2013.09>

Introduction

Canada's innovation performance in the world over the last two decades has been in a state of perpetual decline; moving from among the top performing countries to among the worst performing countries in the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (Council of Canadian Academies, 2009). Executives and policymakers alike are looking for ways to turnaround this dismal performance judging by the extent of changes to Canada's innovation policies and programs over the last two decades. Unfortunately, in spite of the implementation of a variety of new federal and provincial innovation policies and programs to bolster innovation, the situation remains largely unchanged. In 2009, Statistics Canada undertook the *Survey of Innovation and Business Strategy (SIBS)* in order to get a better understanding of the innovation and business strategies of Canadian firms, which could inform innovation policy decisions. This paper presents part of the results from the *Survey of Innovation and Business Strategy* for the textile industry.

The textile industry is one of Canada's oldest manufacturing industries and has been a major contributor to the economy in terms of employment, exports, and

GDP. However, over the last decade, it has been faced with some major challenges, which seem to threaten its continued viability. For instance, the domestic market share of the textile industry has fallen from 70% in the 1980s to about 42% in 2004 and to 36% in 2008. This implies that imports now exceed domestic production by almost 2 to 1. Similarly, employment fell by 45% between 2004 and 2008 (from 44,700 to 24,300), and exports decreased by almost 40% during this period, from \$2.95 billion to \$1.79 billion (Industry Canada, 2011). Further, research and development (R&D) expenditure in the industry fell by almost 20% between 2008 and 2011 - from \$46 million to \$37 million (Statistics Canada, 2012).

The sharp decline in the once vibrant Canadian textile industry can be traced to several global trends that have significantly altered the competitive landscape. Economic and industrial pressures affecting change in the textile industry include technological changes, demand for different products, changes in manufacturing costs, training needs for new workers and employee demographics (Textiles Human Resource Council, 2011). Moreover, globalization and free trade agreements have led to a major restructuring in the industry, which created opportunities for developing countries to play a greater role in the industry. For example, the Multi-Fiber Agreement (MFA), which for decades provided protection for developed countries such as Canada, the United States, and the European Union, was eliminated in 2005, paving the way for increased competition from low-cost producers such as China and India (Ernst, Ferrer and Zult 2005; Martin, 1999). Thus, inefficient, high-cost textile firms in developed countries such as Canada suddenly had to compete directly on price and quality with low-cost producers. Unfortunately, Canadian textile industry found it virtually impossible to win on price against low-cost producers. Thus, Canadian textile firms must find new ways to compete in order to survive and compete in the long-run (Frederick and Cassill, 2009).

Industry observers argue that Canadian textile firms face a tough choice - "be innovative or be dead" (?) since they cannot win on price against low-cost producers like China and India. Innovation involves the introduction of new or significantly improved products, processes, organizational forms, marketing practices (OECD, 2002) and business models (Chesbrough, 2006). According to the Textiles Human Resource Council (2011), textile firms must be willing to change their strategy and invest in new technologies as well as shift their marketing focus from traditional markets to more specialized, high value-added products in order to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage. Textile firms could improve their competitive position by investing in value-adding activities such as R&D, design, production, logistics, marketing and services (Frederick and Cassill, 2009).

Research on the innovation strategies and practices of the Canadian textile industry is very limited. Hence, the goal of this paper is to shed light on the innovation capabilities, strategies and challenges of the textile industry. In this paper, we present and discuss the state of innovation in Canada's textile industry focussing on their business strategies, R&D activities, and products, process, organizational and marketing innovations. The obstacles to innovation and the role of government programs in the textile industry are also highlighted. The remainder of this paper is structured into three sections.

Section 2 provides a brief profile of the textile industry, Section 3 presents the results, and Section 4 discusses the implications of the results and offers the conclusion.

Canada's textile industry

The textile industry is composed of textile mills and textile product mills, represented by NAICS code 313 and 314. There were 2,950 textile enterprises in Canada in 2008 (Statistics Canada Business Register, 2008). The industry is concentrated in the provinces of Ontario and Québec, where 72% of textile firms are located (Textiles Human Resource Council, 2011). The majority of firms in the industry are small in terms of the number of employees. In 2012, approximately 80% of textile firms had less than 10 employees and only about 4% of the firms employed over 100 people (The Conference Board of Canada, 2012).

The main forms of activity performed by firms in this sector are yarn spinning, fabric manufacturing and finishing or dressing, and coating of fabrics and textiles (CTT Group, 2008). Fabrics represent about 93% of the market's total value (Marketline, 2012). Some textile materials are used as inputs into other industries, which are then developed into final products such as cars, medical devices, sports equipment or building materials (Frederick and Cassill, 2009). The industry is highly vertically integrated, with a network that can be divided into four levels. Producers of natural and synthetic fibres are the inputs to textile firms and are found upstream. These firms are involved with the chemical, agricultural, livestock production and mineral industries. Further downstream, the industry deals with companies associated with clothing, upholstered furniture, household items, floor coverings and industrial applications (CTT Group, 2008). Textile firms are also connected to wholesalers, retailers and customers, representing marketing and sales.

There has been an increased emphasis on productivity in the textile industry in response to competition from low-wage countries selling cheaper products (Bloskie, 2005). In 2003, average capital investment was almost \$300 million. However, since then, investment has fallen by almost half and productivity has suffered considerably. The return on capital employed in the textile and clothing industries has fallen from 7.7% in 2002 to 5.3% in 2003. Profit margins peaked at 5% in 2000, but were down to 3.8% in 2003 (Bloskie, 2005). The industry is highly dependent on trade and was deeply affected by the 2008 recession. Profits were already low, and in 2009, due to a drop in sales and exports, they turned negative to the tune of almost 24% (The Conference Board of Canada, 2012).

It is relatively easy for new firms to enter the textile market. Capital requirements are low, and firms produce heterogeneous products, therefore there are many niche markets for textile firms. However, the market favours large firms, as they are better equipped to deal with foreign competition and financing difficulties (The Conference Board of Canada, 2010). In order to gain bargaining power over suppliers and benefit from economies of scale, firms in the industry have been engaging in mergers and acquisitions.

Further, despite falling revenues, firms in the textile industry continue to invest in machinery and new technology, which enables them to remain competitive (Conference Board of Canada, 2012). Canadian textile firms are developing products that are innovative and of a high quality, which makes them difficult to reproduce. However, China’s presence in higher-end textiles and clothing is increasing, and it is expected pose a greater competitive threat to Canadian firms in upcoming years. Another problem that textile firms face is that they are too reliant on a single distributor or retailer, therefore their success lies in the hands of one customer.

In terms of R&D, the focus has been on nine main areas - heat or flame, chemical or biological risk, mechanics and mechanical risks, comfort and functionality, structures and composites, aging, modeling, development of methods or standards, and user response to textile products. Research in textiles is concentrated in Quebec where 40% of the researchers are located (Horne, Dolez and Mlynarek, 2010). Between 2004 and 2008, there were 44 active researchers in textiles and related materials; 43 of them were affiliated with universities, research centres or technical centres (The Institute of Textile Science, 2009). Table 1 provides a snapshot of the research context of the textile industry. Judging by the number of researchers, papers published, and patents obtained, it is clear that textile research is concentrated in three areas – clothing, protection, and medical applications (Horne et al., 2010). Interestingly, the number of patents in the industry is very low with the highest number of four in medical application of textiles.

TABLE 1. RESEARCHERS’ AREAS OF TECHNICAL TEXTILE APPLICATIONS

Application	Researchers	Published Papers	Patents
Clothing	12	35	1
Protection	10	43	2
Medical	7	18	4
Industrial	5	14	0
Transportation	5	2	0
Building	3	13	0
Environmental	3	15	0
Geological	2	8	0
Home	2	3	0
Sports	1	3	0
Packaging	1	0	1
Agriculture	1	0	0

Source: Horne et al. (2010). Textiles Research and Development in Canada

Data

The data for this study comes from the 2009 Statistics Canada Survey of Innovation and Business Strategy. The survey provides statistical information on “strategic decisions, innovation activities and operational tactics used by Canadian firms” (Statistics Canada, 2010). The goal is to aid the government in developing policies to improve productivity and competitiveness by enhancing the understanding of the impact of strategy and innovation on the Canadian

economy. The sample was drawn from the Statistics Canada October 2009 Business Register. A total of 164 firms from the textile industry were surveyed, including 113 small firms (20-99 employees), 33 medium firms (100-250 employees) and 18 large firms (250+ employees).

Survey results

Strategic orientation of textile firms

The only way for textile firms to sustain their competitive position is to innovate and adopt new technologies, which require advanced skills, an educated workforce and capital investments (Frederick and Cassill, 2009). Innovation could provide Canadian textile firms with a competitive edge against their counterparts in developing countries, because this type of competitive advantage is much more difficult to duplicate.

TABLE 2. STRATEGY FOCUS OF CANADIAN FIRMS

Strategic Focus	All	Small	Medium	Large
Most important long-term strategy	%	%	%	%
- Good or Service Positioning	86.6	84.7	90.5	100.0
- Low-price and Cost Leadership	13.4	15.3	9.5	0.0
Strategic Focus with respect to <i>goods and service</i>				
- Maintaining or Expanding Sales	56.1	58.1	52.4	42.2
- Introducing new or improved good or service	39.4	37.1	42.9	57.2
Strategic Focus with respect to <i>marketing</i>				
- Maintaining or intensifying marketing	58.1	62.9	38.1	52.2
- Introducing new or improved methods	36.1	30.6	57.1	47.8
Strategic Focus of <i>operations and business activities</i>				
- Maintain or optimize current operations	56.1	58.9	42.9	56.1
- Introduce new or improved operations	35.6	31.4	52.4	35.6
Strategic Focus of <i>organizational management practices</i>				
- Maintain or optimize practices	57.9	59.7	52.4	57.9
- Introduce new or improved practices	37.0	34.7	42.9	37.0

Source: Data from Statistics Canada Survey of Innovation and Business Strategy, 2009.

The 2009 *Survey of Innovation and Business Strategy* (SIBS) asked respondents a series of questions pertaining to the long-term strategies of their firms as well as the strategic focus of their enterprises in terms of goods and services, marketing, operations, and organizational practices. The distribution of the responses on the various dimensions is shown in Table 2. The results indicate that the long-term strategy for the overwhelming majority of textile firms regardless of firm size is good or service positioning, which focuses on product leadership, product diversification, market segmentation, and quality improvements. Only a small proportion of firms (about 14%) identified low-price and cost-leadership, which is associated with a mass market strategy as their main focus. This finding suggests that most Canadian textile firms have come to the realization that differentiation and innovation rather competing on price and costs are the keys to their long-term survival and competitiveness.

When it comes to the strategic focus with respect to individual components, such as goods or services, marketing, operations and business activities, and organizational and management practices, the overall results indicate textile

firms are more conservative preferring to maintain the status quo rather than introduce improvements. Taking all firms together, it is observed between 56 and 58 percent favor maintaining the current focus with respect goods and services, marketing, operational activities and management practices. However, there are discernible differences when the responses are broken down by firm-size. The data suggest that large firms show a higher tendency for differentiation and innovation (i.e. they are more evenly split between maintaining versus introducing changes) than SMEs, where close to 60 percent prefer maintain the status quo than innovating. This finding appears to be counterintuitive to the widely held view in the innovation literature, which posits that smaller firms tend to be more innovative than larger firms. Interestingly, medium-sized firms show a much greater propensity to introduce innovations in their marketing, operations, and management practices than either large or small firms.

Research & development

The SIBS data in Table 3 indicate that over 90% of medium and large textile firms conduct R&D within their enterprises in Canada compared to 68% of small firms. In terms of R&D conducted outside of Canada either at the company's foreign subsidiary or outsourced, it is observed that 50% of large textile firms conduct overseas R&D compared to just 9.5% of medium firms and 6.4% of small firms. Thus, it seems clear that business R&D in the Canadian textile industry is concentrated in Canada and is done mainly in-house. This finding is consistent with the resourced-based theory of the firm, which suggests that larger enterprises with greater access to resources are more likely to conduct R&D, especially overseas R&D to better serve their overseas customers.

TABLE 3. R&D ACTIVITIES IN CANADIAN TEXTILE FIRMS 2007 - 2009

	All	Small	Medium	Large
Location of R&D	%	%	%	%
- Within Enterprise in Canada (abroad)	72.5 (7.6)	67.7 (4.0)	90.5 (9.5)	91.4 (41.4)
- Outsourced in Canada (abroad)	10.2 (2.6)	11.3 (2.4)	9.5 (0.0)	0.0 (8.6)
Changes in R&D activities in Canada				
- Obtained capacity by merger or acquisition	4.5	4.8	0.0	8.6
- Opened new facility or expanded capacity	7.6	7.3	14.3	0.0
- Closed existing facility or contracted capacity	3.2	2.4	4.8	8.6
- No change	68.0	65.3	81.0	74.1

Source: Data from Statistics Canada Survey of Innovation and Business Strategy, 2009.

The low level of overseas R&D especially among small and medium-sized firms, which dominates the textile industry, raises questions as to whether this limits the ability of Canadian firms to tap in foreign R&D knowledge sources, which could positively impact their innovative capability and long-term competitiveness. Further, over the 2007 - 2009 timeframe, the majority of textile firms, especially larger firms, did not upgrade their R&D capacity. Only

around 12 percent of firms reported changes to their existing capacities through either mergers and acquisition or opening-up new facilities. The high proportion of firms that have not expanded their R&D capacity raises questions about the possible negative long-term effects of such choices.

Innovation practices and strategies

Process innovation

In the Survey, process innovation was defined as the “implementation of new or significantly improved production process, distribution method, or support activity for goods or services” (Statistics Canada, 2010). As shown in Table 4, process innovation is focused primarily on improving manufacturing methods, particularly in larger firms (61.9% and 67.2% for medium and large firms respectively). Far fewer firms, regardless of size, seem to undertake process innovations in logistics, delivery, and supporting activities although larger firms show a greater tendency to adopt process innovations in manufacturing and supply chain management (logistics, delivery, and distribution). A higher proportion of medium firms employed process innovations in supporting activities such as maintenance systems for purchasing, accounting, or computing. Further, most of the process innovations introduced were developed by the firms themselves with larger firms showing greater capability to develop process innovations in-house or in collaboration with others. Only about a quarter of small and medium firms acquired process innovations from an external enterprise or institution.

TABLE 4. PROCESS INNOVATIONS IN CANADIAN TEXTILE FIRMS 2007- 2009

	All	Small	Medium	Large
Process innovation introduced	%	%	%	%
- New or improved methods of manufacturing	50.3	46.8	61.9	67.2
- New or improved logistics, delivery, distribution	15.3	15.3	14.3	17.2
- New or improved supporting activities for process	27.3	26.6	33.3	24.1
Process innovations developed by				
- The enterprise itself	49.4	47.2	53.3	61.5
- The enterprise together with others	25.4	25.0	20.0	38.5
- Other enterprises or institutions	25.2	27.8	26.7	0.0
Average number of new processes introduced	3.7	3.3	6.0	2.3
Total expenditure on process innovations 2009				
- None (\$0)	5.5	2.8	0.0	38.5
- \$1 to less than \$50,000	31.5	34.7	26.7	11.5
- \$50,000 to less than \$150,000	39.0	47.2	20.0	0.0
- \$150,000 to less than \$500,000	11.4	9.7	26.7	0.0
- \$500,000 or more	12.6	5.5	26.7	50.0
Cost reduction & savings due to process innovations				
- Average costs of goods and services reduction (%)	51.5	51.4	53.3	48.7
- Average percentage of cost savings	13.9	15.4	12.1	-

Source: Data from Statistics Canada Survey of Innovation and Business Strategy, 2009.

Although, the average number of process innovations appears to be low, medium-sized firms introduced more process innovations than small and large firms combined. The majority of process innovations employed cost less than \$150,000, with 38% of large firms reporting no expenditure on process innovations; however there is a discernible difference by firm-size in the amount spent on process innovations. Only about 5% of small firms spent more than \$500,000 compared to 26.7% and 50% for medium and large firms. The data also show that process innovations reduced the cost of goods and services by almost 50% and produced cost-savings in the range of 12 to 15 percent for medium and large firms. This result is consistent with the argument that investing in process innovation is important, because it increases operational effectiveness, allowing companies to better utilize their inputs and “perform similar activities better than rivals perform them” (Frederick and Cassill, 2009).

Organizational innovation

“An organizational innovation is a new organizational method in the enterprise’s business practices, workplace organization or external relations that has not been previously used by the enterprise” (Statistics Canada, 2010). Table 5 shows that larger firms are more likely to introduce new business practices for organizing procedures, work responsibilities, decision making, and managing external relations. In all three types of organizational innovations, larger firms outperform smaller firms by a substantial margin. Also, the number of organizational innovations introduced by medium and large firms is more than that of small firms.

TABLE 5. ORGANIZATIONAL INNOVATIONS IN CANADIAN TEXTILE FIRMS 2007-2009

	All	Small	Medium	Large
Types of organizational innovations introduced	%	%	%	%
- New business practices for organizing procedures	37.6	31.5	52.4	75.9
- New methods of organizing work responsibilities & decision making	28.7	25.0	33.3	58.6
- New methods of organizing external relations	17.8	16.9	19.0	25.0
Average number of organizational innovations introduced	2.8	2.4	3.9	3.4

Source: Data from Statistics Canada Survey of Innovation and Business Strategy, 2009.

Good or service innovation

“A product innovation is the market introduction of a new or significantly improved good or service with respect to its capabilities, user friendliness, components or sub-systems” (Statistics Canada, 2010). Table 6 shows that new or significantly improved goods were introduced by about 46% of textile firms while only about 22% of firms introduced service innovations – most of which were produced by smaller firms (22.6% of small firms compared to 8.6% of large firms). Small firms also introduced on average 15 new or significantly improved goods compared to just 7 for large firms. In terms of newness of the

product innovation, 90% of the innovations of medium firms were new to the market compared to roughly 70% for small firms and only 50% for large firms. In this regard, it is also noted that the overwhelming majority of the product innovations in all three firm sizes were new to the enterprise with medium and large firms slightly outperforming small firms. This finding implies that the majority of textile firms regardless of size are focussing on new product innovation. Not surprisingly, large firms develop most of their innovations in-house whereas medium relied more on others working with it to develop new product innovations. Like process innovations, very few textile firms relied on other enterprises or institutions to develop product innovations.

In terms of investments in product innovations, the majority of firms spent less than \$150,000 as was the case with process innovation. Only larger firms seem to have the capability to spend over \$500,000 - 40% and 75% for medium and large firms respectively. These types of innovations can provide firms with a competitive advantage as they provide value-added goods to their customers thereby making it difficult for low-cost competitors to compete with them.

TABLE 6. GOOD OR SERVICE INNOVATIONS IN CANADIAN TEXTILE FIRMS 2007-2009

	All	Small	Medium	Large
Good or service innovations introduced	%	%	%	%
- New or improved goods introduced	45.9	44.3	42.9	66.4
- New or significantly improved services	21.6	22.6	23.8	8.6
Average number of new or significantly improved goods	15.1	15.3	-	6.9
Good and service innovations 2007-2009				
- New to market	70.9	70.7	90.0	50.7
- Only new to enterprise	82.9	81.0	90.0	88.3
Good or service innovations developed by				
- The enterprise itself	64.4	63.8	60.0	74.0
- The enterprise together with others	27.7	25.9	40.0	26.0
- Other enterprises or institutions	7.9	10.3	0.0	0.0
Total expenditure on good or service innovations 2009				
- None (\$0)	9.3	12.1	0.0	0.0
- \$1 to less than \$50,000	29.0	34.5	20.0	0.0
- \$50,000 to less than \$150,000	22.4	27.6	10.0	0.0
- \$150,000 to less than \$500,000	26.2	25.8	30.0	24.7
- \$500,000 or more	13.1	0.0	40.0	75.3

Source: Data from Statistics Canada Survey of Innovation and Business Strategy, 2009

Marketing innovation

“A marketing innovation is the implementation of a new marketing concept or strategy that differs significantly from the enterprise’s existing marketing methods and which had not been used before” (Statistics Canada, 2010). As shown in Table 7, textile firms on the whole did not introduce marketing innovations as commonly as the other types of innovation. In all categories of marketing innovations, only about 1 in 5 firms or less introduced some form of

marketing innovation. Moreover, small and medium-sized textile firms spend less than 20% of their marketing budget on marketing innovations.

TABLE 7. MARKETING INNOVATIONS IN CANADIAN TEXTILE FIRMS

	All	Small	Medium	Large
	%	%	%	%
Marketing innovations introduced between 2007 and 2009				
Significant changes to the aesthetic design or packaging of a good	20.5	21.0	14.3	25.0
New media or techniques for good or service promotion	15.3	15.4	14.3	16.4
New methods for good or service promotion	10.2	8.1	14.3	25.0
New methods of pricing goods or services	20.3	18.5	33.3	17.2
Percentage of marketing expenditure assigned to marketing innovations	18.6	18.8	19.5	-

Source: Data from Statistics Canada Survey of Innovation and Business Strategy, 2009

Collaboration

Collaboration could improve the performance of innovating firms. It is observed from Table 6 that about 27% of textile firms collaborated with other institutions on the introduction of new products or services, which has declined from around 34% reported in Statistics Canada 1999 Survey of Innovation (Hanel and St-Pierre, 2006). It is also noted that medium firms were more deeply engaged in collaboration with 40% of firms compared to both small and large firms with just about 26%. In terms of acquiring good or service innovation from other institutions or firms, about 8% of small firms indicated that they have purchased such innovations.

In terms of process innovations, Table 4 shows that 25.4% of textile firms reported involving others in developing such innovations. However, large firms were more likely to collaborate with other institutions with 38.5% of large firms reporting some form of collaboration compared to 25% and 20% for small and medium firms respectively. In addition, just about 1 in 4 small and medium firms reported that they acquired process innovations developed outside of their enterprise by some other institution. As indicated in Table 4, large firms did not implement any process innovations developed by other firms. This pattern seems to be consistent with the findings of Hanel and St-Pierre (2006), which shows that the probability of collaboration increases with firm size.

Obstacles to Innovation

Table 8 shows that the most widely faced obstacles to innovation in the textile industry are uncertainty and risk (40.8%), small market size (26.5%), lack of skills within the enterprise (25.6%), and lack of internal financing (21.1%). Uncertainty and risk as an obstacle seem to increase with firm size with 67% of large firms compared to 37% of small firms identifying this as the leading

obstacle. Similarly, small market size and lack of internal financing are more acute challenges faced by larger versus smaller firms. Lack of skilled labour within the enterprise appeared to be a major obstacle in 51% of large firms compared to about 22% small firms. In general, the data suggest that large firms face greater obstacles to innovation than small firms, with the exception of regulatory issues and intellectual property rights, which large firms do not see as an obstacle to innovation. The results seem counterintuitive to arguments in the innovation literature that suggests that small firms tend to face greater obstacles to innovation than larger firms, primarily because of financial and other resource constraints.

Innovation scholars often cite problems with access to finance as a major impediment to innovation, especially for small firms (Tourigny and Le, 2004; Larsen and Lewis, 2007); however, this does not seem to be the case for small firms in the Canadian textile industry because only about 18% of small firms reported facing internal and external financing challenges. On the other hand, about 42% of large textile firms indicated that lack of internal financing was an obstacle to innovation and 25% reported that lack of external financing was an impediment to their innovation activities.

TABLE 8. OBSTACLES TO INNOVATION FACED BY CANADIAN TEXTILE FIRMS

	All	Small	Medium	Large
Obstacles to innovation	%	%	%	%
- Market size obstacles to innovation	26.5	20.1	57.1	41.1
- Uncertainty and risk were an obstacle to innovation	40.8	37.0	47.6	67.2
- Lack of skills within the enterprise	25.6	22.6	28.6	50.9
- Internal financing obstacles to innovation	21.1	18.5	43.8	42.2
- External financing obstacles to innovation	19.1	18.6	19.0	25.0
- Finding and reaching agreements with external collaborators	9.5	5.6	19.0	33.6
- Regulatory issues were an obstacle to innovation	14.6	15.3	19.0	0.0
- Intellectual property protection was an obstacle to innovation	13.4	15.3	9.5	0.0
- Government competition policy was an obstacle to innovation	7.0	4.8	14.3	17.2

Source: Data from Statistics Canada Survey of Innovation and Business Strategy, 2009

Government support

There are some differences between large and small firms in the importance they place on various government programs. Government tax credits and grants are the most widely used government programs and are perceived to be the most critical ones for innovative activities by firms in the textile industry. However, it seems that tax credits, while used by 1 in 2 textile firms, is particularly crucial for medium-sized firms where 70% of them ranked it as the most crucial government program (Table 9). In contrast, government grants

are seen as crucial to a higher proportion of smaller firms (23.9%). For large firms, government training, procurement, and technical assistance programs were also ranked as crucial to their innovative activities. Access to government research facilities, market information services and export incentives and services were ranked as crucial by only a very small proportion of small firms (between 1 and 3%).

TABLE 9. GOVERNMENT PROGRAMS FOUND MOST CRITICAL BY TEXTILE FIRMS 2007-2009

Government support programs found most critical	All %	Small %	Medium %	Large %
- Government training programs	9.0	8.5	5.3	19.4
- Government grants	21.0	23.9	15.8	10.2
- Government tax credits	53.9	50.8	73.7	40.8
- Government procurement	3.1	2.8	0.0	10.2
- Government hiring program for recent graduates	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
- Access to government research facilities	2.0	2.8	0.0	0.0
- Government export incentives and services	1.0	1.4	0.0	0.0
- Government information and technical assistance programs	1.1	0.0	0.0	10.2
- Government market information services	2.0	2.8	0.0	0.0

Source: Data from Statistics Canada Survey of Innovation and Business Strategy, 2009

Discussion and conclusion

This paper presents a portrait of the innovation strategies and practices of Canadian textile firms based on Statistics Canada 2009 Survey of Innovation and Business Strategies. Overall, the survey results indicate that there is a huge disconnect between their stated long-term strategy of focussing more on innovation and the actions firms have taken to achieve their goals. The results suggest that the future remains quite challenging unless a more proactive approach is adopted. Canada can no longer compete on price with low cost textile producers from developing countries; therefore the domestic textile industry must develop a clear strategic vision for moving from commodity products to high value-added products and services such as technical textiles¹ (Wyman, 2005). Textile firms need to focus on innovation in order to remain competitive and solidify their position in the industry.

Generally, a firm's long-term strategy serves as the basis for resource allocation decisions and how the activities of the firm are to be organized and executed. This includes the firm's business units, products and services, operational/business activities, and marketing. A close alignment between a

¹ Technical textiles include textiles for automotive applications, medical textiles (e.g., implants), geotextiles (reinforcement of embankments), agrotexiles (textiles for crop protection), and protective clothing (e.g., heat and radiation protection for fire fighter clothing, molten metal protection for welders, stab protection and bulletproof vests, and spacesuits) (www.wikipedia.com).

firm's strategy and its resource allocation could improve its performance. The results of our analysis indicate that the primary long-term strategy of the textile firms is product positioning with a focus on product leadership, market segmentation, product diversification, quality improvements, and high-value added activities. Interestingly, however, almost two-thirds of firms within the industry stated that their strategic focus with respect to goods and service, marketing, operations and business activities, and organizational and management practices is to maintain or expand current activities and practices in these areas rather than innovate. That is, they plan to expand sales of current products and services rather than introduce new or improved ones, intensify current marketing efforts rather than introduce new methods, optimize current operations, business activities, and organizational and management practices instead of implementing new or improved methods and processes. Such misalignments between their overall long-term strategy and their current strategic focus could undermine their competitiveness and ability to respond to changing market dynamics.

Regarding R&D activities within the textile industry, it is observed that at least 80% of firms conduct most of their R&D within Canada and primarily within their own enterprises. Only 10% of R&D is conducted overseas. This pattern of R&D has potentially positive and negative consequences for the industry. On the positive side, there is strong empirical support for a positive relationship between in-house R&D and innovation (Becheikh, Landry and Amara, 2006). Developing in-house R&D is not only important because it enables firms to develop new products and processes, but it also helps firms improve their absorptive capacities, which allows them to better assimilate knowledge from the marketplace (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; Kogut and Zander, 1992). This could positively impact their innovation capabilities. On the other hand, the extremely low level of overseas R&D means that Canadian textile firms are not positioning themselves to leverage the wide range of benefits associated with overseas R&D. Such benefits include access to more talent, knowledge, technologies, foreign research facilities, universities, research networks, markets; being close to the customer; and lower costs (OECD, 1998; Persaud, 2005).

Further, collaboration with other firms or institutions gives firms access to outside knowledge and can act as a sources of innovation. Although, collaboration between trading partners such as vendors and clients are more commonplace, collaboration between firms and universities has been increasing over the past 20 years (Hanel and St-Pierre, 2006). Universities are creators of knowledge and by working with universities textile firms could gain new knowledge and technologies, which they can use to improve innovation and productivity. Industry associations, such as the Textile Federation of Canada and the National Textile Association can also be instrumental in helping firms share information and establish collaborations. However, the evidence of collaboration in new product and process innovation do not appear to be widespread. Within the industry, only about 1 in 4 firms collaborated with others on both product and process innovations; however, larger firms had greater collaborations. This is clearly an area where improvements appear to be warranted.

Investment in human capital, R&D, machinery and equipment can also positively influence innovation, productivity, and growth. One of the reasons why firms may not invest in innovation is that it is difficult for firms to appropriate the benefits from the investment. The social returns to investment are often higher than the private returns on investment (Abdi, 2008). The SIBS results indicate that the overwhelming majority of firms (more than two-thirds) did not add to their R&D capacity in 2009 while about 4% actually closed existing facilities. Only a small fraction of firms (about 10%) expanded their R&D capacity by opening new facilities or through mergers and acquisitions. Even more interesting is the fact that almost 40% of large firms did not spend at all on process innovation while just 10% of firms spent over \$500,000. The results show that firms that spent on process improvements achieved more than 50% reduction in costs of goods and services and about 15% cost savings. This result clearly established the strong positive returns on investment in process improvements, which definitely bolstered the efficiency of these firms thereby increasing their competitiveness. This finding supports the view articulated by Frederick and Cassill (2009) that investment in process innovations can allow companies to better utilize their inputs and perform similar activities better than rivals.

In terms of innovation activities related to goods and services, process, marketing, and organizational innovations, the results show that the industry primary focus is on product and process innovations with very limited attention paid to service innovation, logistics and supply chain, and marketing and organizational innovations. For example, only about 20% of firms introduced a service innovation and even less than that (15%) introduced innovations in logistics and supply chain management. In terms of innovation in organizational and management practices, more than 60% of firms did not introduce any innovations and among those that did, the number of innovations introduced is just 3. Regarding marketing innovations, more than three-quarters of the firms did not introduce any innovation in design or packaging, promotion, or pricing. Moreover, less than 20% of marketing expenditures were devoted to marketing innovations. There is an abundance of research that shows a positive correlation between these types of innovations and firm performance. Thus, textile firms should focus on these types of innovation.

The major obstacles to innovation facing the textile industry are uncertainty and risks, small market size, lack of skills, and internal financing. For large firms, there is the additional obstacle of finding and reaching agreements with external collaborators. Uncertainty and risk as an obstacle to innovation seems like an oxymoron since innovation itself is inherently risky. However, further probing of the business practices of textile firms provides a context for understanding this obstacle. First, the overwhelming majority of suppliers to the industry are from Canada and to a lesser extent the U.S. and Europe. Approximately 95% of the firms rely on Canadian suppliers, usually a single supplier, and 7 out of 10 firms indicate that it would be difficult for them to switch suppliers. Similarly, more than half of the firms that rely on U.S. suppliers indicate that it will be difficult for them to switch suppliers. Such deep concentration of the supply side poses serious risks to the costs and

stability of these firms. Second, on the demand side, it is noted that Canada represents 70% of the market of which 46% are located within the local municipality or province of the firm. The U.S. market is the second largest with 23% followed by Europe with a mere 2%. This huge concentration within the small domestic market not only increases competitive pressures within the industry but also limits growth and pose risks to performance.

Clearly, Canadian textile firms need to not only diverse their supplier base but also to aggressively expand their international customer base by penetrating more deeply into the U.S. market and entering into other markets such as Europe, Asia Pacific and the rest of the world. This could help alleviate the market size obstacle that many firms face. In this regard, it is interesting to observe that even though a substantial proportion of the industry stated market size as a constraint, less than 2% of firms stated that government export incentives and services, market information services, and information and technical assistance programs are crucial to their operations. This situation raises serious questions as to the willingness of the industry to expand internationally and the appropriateness of these government programs to the textile industry.

Government tax credits and grants for innovations were the mostly widely used programs and considered the most crucial to textile firms' innovation efforts, particularly for small and medium firms. Further, despite the shortage of skills, especially in large firms, it is observed that the government *hiring program for recent graduates* was not considered crucial by firms in the industry. Similarly, a mere 2% of firms cited access to government research facilities as crucial to their innovation efforts. Again, this raises questions about the relevance and design and delivery of these initiatives to the textile industry. Further research is needed here to get a clearer understanding of how these programs can be improved to better suit the textile industry.

Notwithstanding, an example of a government program that is specific to the textile industry and that was deemed successful is the *Canadian Apparel and Textiles Industries Program* (CATIP). The program, administered by Industry Canada, ran from 2002 until 2010 and provided funding for firm projects. The Textiles Production Efficiency component (TPEC) received additional funding in the years 2004 and 2005 (Industry Canada, 2009). The program was closely aligned with government policy and aimed to help firms overcome the challenges they were facing due to trade liberalization and competition with low-cost countries. The CATIP program provided funding for firms to identify best practices and introduce new technologies, which would involve both product and process innovation (Industry Canada, 2009). The program was designed to encourage marketing innovation, as it provided funding for firms to develop and implement global marketing strategies. In addition to this, CATIP supported organizational innovation by helping firms develop business plans and undertake market surveys in order to access capital. In total, the program funded 850 projects in 444 firms; 40% were aimed at increasing productivity and 30% of the projects helped firms identify and adopt innovative best practice (Industry Canada, 2009). According to Industry Canada's *Final Program Evaluation Report*, 76% of the firms would have been unlikely to complete their projects without financing from CATIP (Industry

Canada, 2009). This example seems to suggest that government's assistance to the industry could be more effective if it is more targeted rather than more general programs designed for all manufacturing industries.

From a research perspective, this study revealed that medium firms are distinctly different from small firms in their innovative capability, challenges and performance. This observation therefore raises questions as to whether the common practice of classifying medium firms with small firms under the "SMEs" title from the perspective of innovation policies and programs is appropriate. In this study, medium firms show greater capability for undertaking in-house R&D, spent more on process and product innovation, introduced more process innovations, introduced substantially more *new-to-market* and *new-to-enterprise* product innovations, collaborated more, and faced greater obstacles pertaining to market size, internal financing, skills, and reaching external collaboration agreements. Medium firms also make significantly greater use of government tax credits and less use of government grants. Although, the evidence in the empirical literature on the link between firm size and innovation is mixed, policy makers continue to design SMEs policies, which tend to favour small firms rather than medium firms (Munn-Venn and Mitchell, 2005). This issue needs further examination.

To expand this study, research could be conducted to compare the Canadian textile industry to other industries in the manufacturing sector, or to the textile industries of other developed countries, such as the US, Germany, and Norway. This would allow us to benchmark the Canadian textile industry and see how successful it is with respect to innovation. A limitation of the SIBS data is that it only include firms with more than 20 employees, however, about 80% of Canadian textile firms have less than 20 employees. Therefore, to have a complete understanding of the textile industry, we would need to collect data from smaller firms as well.

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